

Multiwavelength excitation Raman scattering study of Sb₂Se₃ compound: fundamental vibrational properties and secondary phases detection

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Abstract

This work presents a complete analysis of Raman active modes of Sb₂Se₃ measured by six different excitation wavelengths from NIR to UV, under different polarization configurations and at low temperature. Simultaneous fitting of spectra allowed the deconvolution and identification of the 28 Raman peaks obtained in monocrystalline Sb₂Se₃ sample from the 30 modes predicted by the group theory analysis for this crystalline structure. Analysis of the spectra measured under different polarization configurations yielded the preliminary assignment of the peaks symmetry, while the measurements under low temperature resulted in a fine resolution of the peaks in Raman spectra. Additionally, evaluation of the spectra of the most probable secondary phases under different excitation wavelengths allowed to define the most appropriate measurement conditions for experimental discrimination of their Raman peaks in the spectra of Sb₂Se₃ based thin films solar cells. The combination of different wavelength allows a non-destructive methodology for high sensitivity detection of main secondary phases of the Sb₂Se₃.

Keywords: Sb₂Se₃, 1D material, Raman scattering, vibrational properties, single crystal, thin film, solar cell.

Introduction

Recently, Sb_2Se_3 (Antimonselite) has become a relevant earth abundant semiconductor material with different possible technological applications such as superconductivity,¹ electronic components,² electrode for sodium ion batteries,³ photodetectors⁴ and as emerging thin film solar cell absorber.⁵⁻⁸ In particular, in case of photovoltaic application, the material has shown remarkable improvement in the last few years, demonstrating solar cells in substrate configuration with conversion efficiencies exceeding 9 %.⁹ This, together with appropriate material properties,¹⁰ has opened the perspectives for its use in solar energy conversion application.

One of the most interesting peculiarities of Sb_2Se_3 is that this material is a 1D (one dimensional) semiconductor, and is formed by $[\text{Sb}_4\text{Se}_6]_n$ ribbons where the {Se-Sb-Se-Sb-Se} chains present a strong covalent bonding between Sb and Se atoms, but the different $[\text{Sb}_4\text{Se}_6]_n$ ribbons are bonded through relatively weak van der Waals forces. This 1D structure confers interesting anisotropic properties that can be very relevant for photovoltaic applications, because in one direction it exhibits an electrical conductivity much higher than in the two other directions.^{10,11} In addition, the material has orthorhombic structure (space group $Pnmb$, with $a = 11.62 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.77 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.962 \text{ \AA}$),¹² which is the solely Sb-Se known stable phase at typical conditions required for the synthesis and crystallization of the material (temperature and pressure). This is of key importance because implies that no structural polymorphs, neither large amount of secondary phases are expected in this system, simplifying thus its synthesis and technological applications.

In fact, Sb_2Se_3 has shown a high degree of flexibility in terms of synthesis methods as it is typical for other chalcogenide materials, and it can be easily grown by chemical¹³⁻¹⁵ and physical^{5,6,16,17} routes. Nevertheless, Sb_2Se_3 evaporates congruently, presenting a relatively high vapour pressure at common processing temperatures.¹⁸ This makes very attractive all the physical vapour deposition methods that can be employed at relatively low temperatures (300 – 400 °C), for the growth of high-quality thin films. Indeed, most of the solar cells with decent efficiencies reported so far, have been prepared using physical vapour deposition methods.^{5-8,19-22}

Even if the material presents a single stable phase at normal conditions, and the occurrence of secondary phases is minimal in binary compounds, the relatively complex structure of the material organized in 1D ribbons as well as the relatively low temperatures required for its

synthesis (~350 °C), suggest the possibility of formation of point defects (antisites, interstitials etc.), and possible contaminating phases (like elemental Se, Sb and its oxides), that can be detrimental for the overall performance of the solar cells. In this sense, and considering the early stages on the development of the compound, a deep analysis on the fundamental structural properties of Sb_2Se_3 is of high importance.

In this context Raman spectroscopy has demonstrated to be a powerful tool for characterization of new chalcogenide compounds for thin film photovoltaic application.²³⁻²⁶ It has proven also its suitability as a tool for the deep characterization of the denoted as van der Waals solids or 2D materials such as graphene, MoS_2 , WS_2 , As_2S_3 , and 1D materials such as Te.²⁷⁻³⁰ This suitability is related to the strong impact in the vibrational properties of the anisotropic character of these materials. For example, due to the modifications in the obtained spectra with the amount of layers present in the sample, being able to differentiate the effects of the interlayer coupling to investigate the fine structure, atomic bonds, and mechanical and thermal properties of 2D materials.²⁹ In the case of 1D materials, like Te, it has been reported a shift in some of the Raman modes associated to the presence of strain.³⁰ Under our knowledge few materials have been evaluated, however the high anisotropy is expected to induce strong effects in the Raman spectra allowing the use of this tool for the characterization of 1D structures, like $\text{Sb}_2(\text{S,Se})_3$.

Furthermore, sensibility of phonon to the crystallographic changes allows to provide relevant information about the presence of secondary phases, composition, crystal quality and presence of defects in the analysed material. However, a fingerprint spectrum of the Sb_2Se_3 measured under different conditions is missing up to date, and only few works are available with very limited information.^{12,31} In this work, a complete multi-wavelength Raman scattering analysis of the Sb_2Se_3 thin films and commercial single crystal, as well as of the possible secondary phases, using excitation wavelengths from the NIR (1064 nm) down to UV (325 nm) was carried out. In addition, the measurements on a monocrystalline sample were measured under different polarization configurations and at low temperatures. As result the complete identification of most of the Raman modes of the compound was performed, as well as the most appropriate conditions for the detection of possible secondary phases were proposed.

Experimental details

The study presented in this work was achieved using both, a commercial Sb_2Se_3 single crystal from 2D semiconductors (figure 1A), as well as thin films synthesized at IREC (figure

1B). The synthesis was performed onto Mo coated soda-lime glass (SLG/Mo) substrate, with a Mo tri-layer metallic contact preparation as it has been described elsewhere.³² Sb_2Se_3 was synthesized using a sequential process consisting in the thermal evaporation of 200 nm of Sb (Alfa Aesar, Sb shots 1-3 mm, Puratronic, 6N metal basis) using an Oerlikon Univex 250 evaporator, with a base vacuum of 5×10^{-5} mBar and an evaporation rate of 0.7 \AA/s . The SLG/Mo/Sb precursors were then submitted to a reactive annealing in a tubular furnace under Se atmosphere using semi-closed graphite boxes (23 cm^3). For this purpose, $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ in area samples were heated up to $320 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a heating ramp of $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/s}$, and kept at this temperature during 30 min, and then cooled down naturally (taking approximately 1 hour). During the annealing, 30 mg of Se (Alfa Aesar, Se powder 200 mesh, 5N metal basis) were used and 500 mBar of total Ar pressure was imposed. Half of the sample was used to produce and characterize solar cells (SLG/Mo/ Sb_2Se_3 /CdS/i-ZnO/ITO), and the other half for the fundamental characterization.

Figure 1: A) Sb_2Se_3 single-crystal optical image. B) FE-SEM cross-section image from the Sb_2Se_3 complete device.

The solar cells were characterized by illuminated J-V curves using a calibrated AAA class Abet Sun 3000 solar simulator.

Additionally, the Sb shots and Se powder converted into pellets and described before, as well as Sb_2O_3 (Alfa Aesar, powder, 5N puratronic metal basis), where also used for the complete Raman characterization.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) results were obtained with a PANalytical X'Pert PRO MPD Bragg-Brentano powder diffractometer equipped with a Cu tube operating at 45 kV and 40 mA, a Ge (111) Johansson type primary focalizing monochromator and a silicon strip 1D X'Celerator detector. High resolution, high statistics, full angular range $\text{Cu K}\alpha_1$ $\theta/2\theta$ scans are obtained: $2\theta/\theta$ scans from 4 to 145° 2θ ; step size 0.0166° ; measuring time per step 200 seconds (X'Celerator active length 2.113°); 5 consecutive repeated scans; total measuring time per

sample 19 hours. Two samples were measured: a fine powder sample obtained after grinding, in an Agate mortar, a small piece of the commercial Sb_2Se_3 single crystal, mounted in the cylindrical cavity (0.15 mm of height and 16 mm of diameter) of a zero-background silicon single crystal sample holder; a thin film sample, on a piece of about $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^2$, with a stack SLG/Mo/ Sb_2Se_3 . Full profile analysis, Rietveld method,³³ have been done in both Sb_2Se_3 powder and SLG/Mo/ Sb_2Se_3 XRD data. The refinements have been performed by the TOPAS v5 software.³⁴ The background is modelled with a 20th order Chebyshev polynomial. The instrumental contribution to the diffraction profile is calculated with the Fundamental Parameters Approach.³⁵

Raman measurements have been performed using IREC developed Raman setups optimized for the UV-Visible spectral region (based on Horiba Jobin Yvon FHR640 monochromator) and NIR-IR region (based on Horiba Jobin Yvon iHR320 monochromator). The first system is coupled with an open electrode CCD detector cooled down to $-75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the second with NIR enhanced CCD detector cooled down to $-75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and also an InGaAs array detector cooled to liquid nitrogen temperature for the measurements obtained with the 1064 nm excitation wavelength. The utilization of different gratings for the light dispersion allows to optimize the spectra resolution, achieving a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the main peak of monocrystalline silicon at 520 cm^{-1} of $4 - 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for most of the excitation wavelengths, except for UV measurements (325 nm) where silicon FWHM was about 8 cm^{-1} . The study was performed with laser power density below 10 W/cm^2 by using a macro-spot with a diameter in the range of $50 - 70 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ depending on the excitation wavelength. Finally, the use of unpolarised laser beam allowed to minimize the impact of the crystalline orientation in the Raman spectra. Measurements under different polarization conditions were performed using the LabRam HR800-UV system from Horiba Jobin Yvon with polarization filters. A close cycle helium cryostat was used to decrease the sample temperature down to 10 K while obtaining the Raman spectra using the FHR640 based system.

Results and discussion

Structural characterization of single crystal and thin film Sb_2Se_3

Sb_2Se_3 *Antimonselite* is isostructural with Sb_2S_3 *Stibnite*. The crystal structure is orthorhombic, space group *Pnmb* (#62), $Z = 4$, with twenty atoms in the primitive unit cell, all the atoms of the asymmetric unit (two non-equivalent Sb cation sites and three non-equivalent Se anions sites) in the Wyckoff Position $4c (x,y,1/4)$.³⁶ The Rietveld analysis, in the XRD data

of the Sb_2Se_3 powder sample from the single crystal, confirms that the sample shows only one phase with the expected above described structure. The structure has been refined with the values of $R_{\text{wp}} = 7.65$ and $R_{\text{B}} = 3.18$ and the Rietveld plot is presented in the figure 2A. In the table S1 are reported the XRD indexation. The 18 refined structural parameters, three cell parameters, ten atomic coordinates and five isotropic temperature parameters, are listed in table 1 and 2 together with the resulting bond distances. Crystallographic results agree with previous publications.³⁶ The crystal structure and detailed atomic base, with indication of non-equivalent positions, and the distance between them obtained from the Rietveld analysis are shown in figure 3. It is interesting to mention, that all the bonds in the $[\text{Sb}_4\text{Se}_6]_n$ ribbons have relatively close distance,³⁶ which shrinks the distribution of phonons energy and makes them hardly resolvable.

Figure 2: Rietveld refinement (red) of an XRD pattern (black) and difference between observed and calculated (green) of: A) Sb_2Se_3 powder from single crystal; B) $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{Mo}/\text{SLG}$ thin film stack.

Figure 3: A) Crystal structure of Sb_2Se_3 ($Pnmb$, #62). B) Non-equivalent atomic site in each $[Sb_4Se_6]_n$ atomic chains and short intra-chain Se-Sb bonds.

Table 1: Sb_2Se_3 crystallographic parameters and refinement agreement factors.

	Structure, space group, Z	R_{wp}	R_B	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	V/Z (Å ³)
Powder	Orthorhombic, $Pnmb$, 4	7.65	3.178	11.63636(9)	11.78446(6)	3.97882(3)	545.607(7)	136.4
Thin film	Orthorhombic, $Pnmb$, 4	6.51	2.809	11.6286(2)	11.77636(14)	3.97617(4)	544.506(13)	136.1

Table 2: Atomic coordinates, site occupation factor and Wyckoff positions of the non-equivalent atoms, and bond distances in between them obtained from the refinement of the diffractogram of monocrystalline powder sample.

Name	Element	X	Y	Z	B_{eq}	sof	Wyck.	bound	Dist. (Å)
Sb(I)	Sb	0.32796(11)	0.02997(7)	0.25000	1.18(3)	1.00	4c	Sb(I)-Se(II)	2.679
Sb(II)	Sb	0.03938(12)	0.14743(8)	0.75000	1.23(3)	1.00	4c	Sb(I)-Se(II)	2.664
Se(I)	Se	0.87102(18)	0.05430(12)	0.25000	0.92(4)	1.00	4c	Sb(II)-Se(I)	2.596
Se(II)	Se	0.44461(17)	0.12954(11)	0.75000	0.93(4)	1.00	4c	Sb(II)-Se(III)	2.802
Se(III)	Se	0.1950(2)	0.21399(12)	0.25000	1.07(4)	1.00	4c		

In contrast to powder samples, the phase analysis in the X-ray diagram of the thin film stack of SLG/Mo/ Sb_2Se_3 (figure 2B), confirms the presence of Sb_2Se_3 as the main observed phase in the layer and the Mo back contact underneath. Additionally, minor contributions identified as elemental Se secondary phase of the Sb_2Se_3 layer and the formation of small amount of $MoSe_2$ in the Sb_2Se_3 /Mo interface are observed. All four observed phases were included in the Rietveld analysis. All the structural parameters of Sb_2Se_3 , but the a , b and c unit cell parameters, i.e. the atomic coordinates and the six temperature parameters, are fixed equal to the obtained ones in the crystal structure refinement of the powder Sb_2Se_3 sample (see table 2). The Rietveld

refinement is fully reasonable with excellent agreement factors $R_{wp} = 6.51$; $R_B(\text{Mo}) = 3.18$; $R_B(\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3) = 2.81$ and Rietveld plot is shown in figure 2B. The Sb_2Se_3 *Antimonselite* is the main phase of the analysed absorber and does not show strong preferential texture, indicating close to random orientation distribution of the crystals that can be observed in the random orientation of the crystal's facets in the SEM (image figure 1B). On the other hand, no significant peak broadening is observed in comparison with the single crystal powder. This suggest a high crystal quality of the Sb_2Se_3 crystals, in agreement with large size (>500 nm) and geometrical shape of the Sb_2Se_3 grains observed in SEM cross-section (figure 1B). The obtained cell parameters and volume of the Sb_2Se_3 thin film were found to be slightly compressed in respect to the ones of the powder sample (see table 1).

Vibrational properties of Sb_2Se_3 single crystal

Group theory analysis of the Sb_2Se_3 with *Pnmb* space group yields 60 different phonon modes split on three acoustic modes, and fifty-seven optical modes, including thirty Raman active, twenty-two IR active and five silent modes:^{37,38}

$$\Gamma_{\text{acoustic}} = B_{1u} \otimes B_{2u} \otimes B_{3u}; \Gamma_{\text{Raman}} = 10A_g \otimes 5B_{1g} \otimes 10B_{2g} \otimes 5B_{3g}; \Gamma_{\text{IR}} = 9B_{1u} \otimes 4B_{2u} \otimes 9B_{3u}; \Gamma_{\text{silent}} = 5A_u$$

The Raman spectrum of Sb_2Se_3 single crystal measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength is shown in figure 4A. In the range 45 – 300 cm^{-1} the non-polarized (un-Pol) spectrum is dominated by a large band at 190 cm^{-1} and seven less intense bands, some of them being strongly overlapped. For higher wavenumbers no additional fundamental bands are observed and only second order of the main band can be detected. Detection of only eight bands contradicts the expected thirty Raman active modes and is related to a complex structure of the observed bands with a high overlapping of the individual peaks. In order to decompose the observed bands and analyse the symmetry type of the peaks, measurements using different polarization configurations were obtained, presented in the bottom of figure 4A. The Raman polarizability tensors for the point group *mmm* (D_{2h}) are:

$$A_g: \begin{pmatrix} a & & \\ & b & \\ & & c \end{pmatrix} \quad B_{1g}: \begin{pmatrix} & & d \\ & & \\ d & & \end{pmatrix} \quad B_{2g}: \begin{pmatrix} & & e \\ & & \\ e & & \end{pmatrix} \quad B_{3g}: \begin{pmatrix} & & & \\ & & & \\ & & & f \\ & & f & \end{pmatrix}$$

Taking these tensors into account the following selection rules for the primitive crystal planes, like (100), (010) and (001), for the peak symmetry assignment can be deduced using the Porto notations:³⁹

- i) The Raman peaks which show maximum intensity in parallel polarization configurations, $\langle \bar{Z}|XX|Z \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{Z}|YY|Z \rangle$, and conversely less intensity in cross polarization configurations, $\langle \bar{Z}|XY|Z \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{Z}|YX|Z \rangle$, can be assigned to A_g modes.
- ii) The peaks with the inverse behaviour, maximum intensity in $\langle \bar{Z}|XY|Z \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{Z}|YX|Z \rangle$ configurations and minimum in $\langle \bar{Z}|XX|Z \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{Z}|YY|Z \rangle$ configurations can be assigned to B_{1g} , B_{2g} or B_{3g} modes.

Figure 4: A) Room temperature Raman spectra of the Sb_2Se_3 single crystal measured under the 532 nm excitation wavelength in non-polarized (un-Pol) and with different polarization configurations (indicated above the graph with Porto notations). For the non-polarized spectra an example of the fitting function (red curve) with independent Lorentzian peaks (green curves) and difference between the fitted and the measured spectra (blue curve) are presented. B) Room temperature non-polarized multi-wavelength Raman spectra of the Sb_2Se_3 single crystal. Numbers in both figures correspond to the order number of the peaks in table 3; asterisk denotes a peak close to the filter cut that cannot be assured to belong to the Sb_2Se_3 system.

Assuming that strong change in the peaks intensity in parallel and cross polarization is related with the measurements from one of the primitive crystal plains, the tentative assignment of the peaks is proposed in table 3. Note, that the measurements were performed on the relatively small crystal plane, which prohibited to measure its strict crystallographic orientation with a conventional X-ray diffraction equipment. However, a strong difference in the spectra

measured in parallel and cross polarizations allows to suppose that one of the primitive crystal planes was used in the case. Further, the differences in intensities between the $\langle \bar{Z}|XX|Z \rangle$ and $\langle \bar{Z}|YY|Z \rangle$ configurations can be explained by differences between a , b and c elements of the Raman tensor of A_g modes. Due to the high anisotropic properties of the 1D material, the polarizability tensor elements of the A_g symmetry modes may be quite different which would explain the difference in intensity of the peaks assigned to this modes in spectra measured along different crystallographic orientations. This way, the highest difference is expected between the spectra measured along and across to the orientation of the ribbons. On the other hand, no significant changes in the intensity of B_{xg} ($x = 1 - 3$) symmetry peaks are expected in the spectra measured along or across to the 1D ribbons. This opens the possibility of estimation of the preferential orientation of the ribbons in a polycrystalline sample, which is one of the critical points of Sb_2Se_3 material.¹⁰ However, an analysis of the samples with different ribbon orientation should be performed to prove the proposed application of the Raman spectra.

The origin of the Raman peaks overlapping come from the strong similarities between the different Sb and Se atoms in non-equivalent positions with very similar but non-equal bond length (figure 3B and table 2). Aside with the non-equivalent positions, the presence of the 30 expected Raman modes in a very small region ($20 - 220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) brings the necessity of high-resolution Raman spectroscopy for the proper observation of the Raman modes. Therefore, the available gratings with higher dispersive power for the different excitation wavelengths were used in order to achieve the highest resolution possible in this work. Furthermore, the Raman spectra of Sb_2Se_3 single crystal were measured using 6 different excitation wavelengths. The methodology of simultaneously fitting using a multi-wavelength excitation reported by Dimitrievska et al.^{23,36} allowed to perform a precise deconvolution of the Raman spectra to the Lorentzian peaks, assuming the good crystal quality of the single crystal. Using this methodology, 15 peaks from the total 30 theoretically expected Raman modes were resolved at room temperature. Different intensities of the peaks or even appearance of new peaks can be observed in figure 4B, depending on the excitation wavelength. Enhancement of different peaks under different excitations is due to the coupling of the excitation wavelength with an inter-band optical transition at the Γ point. Based on theoretical calculations the latter were found to have the energies $\Gamma_1 = 1.21 \text{ eV}$, $\Gamma_3 = 1.5 \text{ eV}$, $\Gamma_5 = 2.0 \text{ eV}$, $\Gamma_7 = 2.25 \text{ eV}$, $\Gamma_{14} = 2.8 \text{ eV}$ that can be coupled with $\lambda_{ex} = 1064, 785, 633, 532$ and 442 nm respectively.¹² Even assuming small discrepancies of the theoretically calculated values with the real position of the energy levels a close to resonant effect is still expected for the mentioned excitation wavelengths.

Herein the non-equivalent enhancement of the peaks in resonant conditions can be explained by difference in the atoms, producing the specific vibrational phonon, and their involvement in creation of specific energy level.

As it is mentioned above, a simultaneous Lorentzian fitting of the Raman spectra measured under different excitations was performed for the fine spectra deconvolution. This was done by using the minimum number of peaks, which can describe the whole measured spectrum. Additionally, the FWHM of the peaks was maintained between spectra, allowing to achieve similar fitting equation for all excitation wavelengths. The observed differences between spectra are summarized hereafter. First, an asymmetric broadening towards the lower wavenumber side of the main peak was observed in the spectra measured with 442 and 532 nm excitation wavelengths, suggesting the existence of a peak at the red side of the main peak found at 184.7 cm^{-1} . The peaks at 80.1 , 100.1 and 132.2 cm^{-1} are found to be better resolved in the spectra measured under 442 nm excitation wavelength in comparison with the other wavelengths. Additionally, a shoulder at the red side of the main peak can be seen around 174 cm^{-1} , although the fitting of this peak was not possible. The measurement performed with the usual 532 nm excitation wavelength resulted in one of the richest spectra and its fitting is presented as example in figure 4A. Here, the peaks at 80.1 , 100.1 , 132.2 and 212.8 cm^{-1} can be finely resolved. For the 633 nm wavelength a broad band close to 153 cm^{-1} has the highest intensity, also the contrast with FWHM of this band measured under 442 nm excitation wavelength and a red shift mean the presence of more than one peak at this frequency. An enhancement of the peaks intensity at 80.1 , 118.7 and 212.8 cm^{-1} was found in the spectra measured under 785 nm excitation wavelength. Additionally, under this excitation conditions the most intense band at 191.5 cm^{-1} has the lowest FWHM from all the investigated spectra, which assumes the weak intensity of the peaks around the main mode. Finally, excitation with the 1064 nm wavelength implies near resonant conditions due to close energy of the laser with the optical bandgap of the material. Under this measurement conditions the best signal to noise ratio was observed and the peak at 118.7 cm^{-1} exhibits the higher intensity comparing to spectra measured with other excitation wavelengths. In the table 3 wavenumbers of all found peaks are summarized together with the most suitable excitation wavelength for observation. The latter were determined after overlapping of measured spectra normalized to the peak at 191.5 cm^{-1} (see figure 5). Some of the Raman peak frequencies were previously published in different works (see the references in table 3) and are in agreement with the present study, and with the theoretical predictions of the peaks wavenumbers from DFT calculations (extracted from

phonon branch diagram collecting all modes: acoustic, infrared and Raman active).⁴⁰ However, in our study, no peak around 250 cm^{-1} was detected under any excitation conditions, and no vibrational mode was predicted in the theoretical calculations close to this position, indicating the misinterpretation of the spectra analysis reported previously by many authors.^{2,15,16,41-48}

Figure 5: Normalized Raman scattering spectra of Sb_2Se_3 measured under different excitation wavelength at room temperature. The coloured arrows indicate the best excitation wavelength for observation of a specific peak.

Figure 6: Evolution of the Raman scattering spectra of Sb_2Se_3 under 325 nm excitation wavelength measured at room temperature with the least power density available (0.25 W/cm^2). Increase of the intensity of a broad band around 254 cm^{-1} , assigned to the amorphous selenium ($a\text{-Se}$), is associated with degradation of Sb_2Se_3 under UV light.

The sixth excitation wavelength used in the present study is the 325 nm laser line. Under this excitation conditions, a degradation of the material is observed starting from the lowest laser power density available 0.25 W/cm^2 (figure 6). This degradation is characterized by the reduction of the intensity and broadening of the FWHM of the Sb_2Se_3 Raman peaks, and by a concomitant increase of the intensity of peak at 254.8 cm^{-1} associated with amorphous Se (a -

Se) secondary phase (figure 6). The observed time evolution of the spectra suggests a decomposition of the Sb_2Se_3 phase due to break of the compound bonds under UV excitation.

Table 3: Frequency of the Raman peaks obtained from the multi-wavelength analysis of spectra measured at room temperature (RT) and at low temperature (10 K), best excitation conditions and tentative symmetry assignment. Previously published experimental and theoretical results are presented for comparison.

#	Symm.	λ_{ex} [nm]	This work				References			
			Raman shift (RT) [cm^{-1}]	FWHM (RT) [cm^{-1}]	Raman shift (10 K) [cm^{-1}]	FWHM (10 K) [cm^{-1}]	37** [cm^{-1}]	46 [cm^{-1}]	38 [cm^{-1}]	1 [cm^{-1}]
							20/29/40/44/45/46/48			
1	B_{Xg}	532	54.4	2.0			55/56			
2	A_{g}	532	61.6	2.4			58/59/ 60×2/61			
3		532*			71.9	1.3	69×2			
4		532*			74.7	2.4				
5		532*			76.0	1.6	76			
6		532*			78.5	0.4	77			
7	A_{g}	785	80.1	2.9	83.4	1.7	84	80	84	
8		532*			91.2	1.9	92			
9		532*			94.9	1.0	93/94			
10	B_{Xg}	532	97.6	3.8	99.5	2.0	99			
11	A_{g}	442/532	100.1	3.8	103.3	2.5	102/103			105
12	B_{Xg}	442	102.6	6.7	107.2	1.3	110			
13	B_{Xg}	785	109.3	13.0	111.4	1.8	113			
14		532*			114.7	2.1				
15	A_{g}	1064/785	118.7	8.7	119.0	2.4	118/119	120	117	
16		532*			122.9	1.0	124/125			122.6
17	B_{Xg}	633	125.7	12.3	130.0	2.7	129/131/132/134×3			131
18	B_{Xg}	532	132.2	14.0	138.7	1.0	142/145/146×2			
19	B_{Xg}	532	154.4	13.2	157.4	3.5	158	151		155.2
20		532*			164.0	4.3	164			
21		532*			168.3	0.9	170			
22		532*			174.7	6.9	174/175×2			
23		532*			182.7	6.4	179×2			181
24	A_{g}	532	184.7	11.5	189.1	2.0	188			
25	A_{g}	532	191.5	10.6	195.8	2.9	194/195	189	193	189.6
26		532*			203.7	3.9	200/201			
27	--	633/1064	207.8	7.3	209.0	3.3	207			
28	A_{g}	532	212.8	6.0	215.6	3.1	214	210		213.3

*The peak was resolved only in the spectra measured at 10 K.

**Position of all optical modes, both IR and Raman active, were extracted from the phonon branch diagram at the zone centre Γ -point.

Apart to the peaks' frequency, their FWHM is also presented in the table 3. Here the strong difference in the peaks width could be an indication for the more complex structure of the wide peaks ($\text{FWHM} > 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In order to resolve the complex structure mentioned above low temperature Raman measurement at $\sim 10 \text{ K}$ were carried out (see figure 7). The reduction on thermal dispersion of the phonon states ($\Gamma_0 + \Delta\Gamma(T)$) (anharmonic contributions) minimizes the overlapping of the different peaks, thus reducing the FWHM, allowing the identification of 26 peaks under 532 nm excitation wavelength. In addition, the reduction of thermal agitation of the lattice implies a blue-shift in frequencies for the peaks, meaning that this analysis is useful for fundamental characterization of the material's vibrational properties, but not as a quality control tool for sample analysis purposes like the multi-wavelength study at room temperature described above. Nevertheless, the measurement at low temperature is suitable to corroborate the peak assignment to the room temperature measurements. All these new peaks detected at low temperature are added in table 3. For example, in spectra measured at low temperature a series of new peaks in the spectral range $60 - 80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were found (at $71.9, 74.7, 76.0, 78.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), while only two peaks (at 61.6 and 80.1 cm^{-1}) were resolved in the spectra measured at room temperature. We can observe the corroboration of the predictions done for the band around 100 cm^{-1} at room temperature and under different excitations, which correlate well with the low temperature measurements (taking into account the blue-shift), confirming the hypothesis of 3 peaks which form this band. The band between $100 - 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is also properly identified in the multi-wavelength analysis and two peaks more can be resolved at positions 114.7 and 122.9 cm^{-1} . The broad peak at 154.4 cm^{-1} is deconvoluted into two different peaks at positions 157.4 and 164.0 cm^{-1} . The shoulder on the low wavenumbers side of the main peak at low temperatures is resolved into two different peaks at 168.3 and 174.7 cm^{-1} . The main mode as stated in the analysis above is composed of three peaks at positions $182.7, 189.1$ and 195.8 cm^{-1} , the latter being the most intense one. Finally the higher energy peaks are confirmed by the low temperature analysis and another peak is found at 203.7 cm^{-1} . The FWHM of the peaks is considerably lower than the room temperature measured ones, and very consistent ranging from $0.4 - 4.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the exception of the peaks at 174.7 and 182.5 cm^{-1} with FWHM of 6.5 cm^{-1} that could account for the 2 peaks left to find. As it can be seen in table 3 there is strong correlation of the theoretically calculated frequencies of Raman modes and the peaks positions measured in the low temperature spectra. These 26 obtained peaks, plus 2 peaks at low wavenumbers 54.4 and 61.6 cm^{-1} , give a total of 28 resolved peaks from 30 predicted by group theory analysis.

Figure 7: Low temperature (10 K) Raman spectra measured under 532 nm excitation wavelength (black dots). Green lines represent individual peaks fitting with Lorentzian functions, and the red line depicts total fitting function. Intensity of the main peak is cut to emphasis the low intensity peaks. Numbers correspond to the order number of the peaks in table 3. Inset: full experimental spectra (black dots), total fitted spectra (red line) and difference between them (blue line).

Secondary phase analysis

The only stable phase of Sb-Se system has orthorhombic Sb_2Se_3 ($Pnmb$, #62) structure and no other structural or compositional polymorphs has been reported to our knowledge. The only expected secondary phases are pure selenium (amorphous or trigonal), pure antimony and antimony oxide Sb_2O_3 . The later, antimony oxide, is alike to selenium containing compound has 3 different crystallographic structures, α - Sb_2O_3 , β - Sb_2O_3 , γ - Sb_2O_3 , which are the most stable polymorphs, and no less energetically favourable Sb_2O_4 and Sb_2O_5 phase are expected to form as secondary phases in Sb_2Se_3 .⁵⁰

The main Raman peaks of some of the mentioned secondary phases are summarized in table 4, with indication of the most suitable wavelength for their detection. Taking into account the temperature conditions usually used for the Sb_2Se_3 synthesis (< 400 °C) the most stable oxide contain polymorph is cubic α - Sb_2O_3 (senarmonite). However, formation of high temperature stable orthorhombic β - Sb_2O_3 (valentinite) polymorph cannot be excluded. The Raman spectra of both phases were studied by Cody et al.⁵¹ and the spectra from commercial powder of β - Sb_2O_3 was measured in the present study, and a 442 nm excitation wavelength was found as the most suitable for these secondary phases detection. The third possible γ - Sb_2O_3 was found only under specific high-pressure conditions and is not expected to be formed during the Sb_2Se_3 synthesis, with the actual state of the art processes. Measurements of elemental Se and Sb were performed under 633 nm excitation wavelength, which showed to be the most appropriate for detection of these phases. In case of elemental selenium two phases, crystalline trigonal selenium (t-Se) and amorphous selenium (a-Se), can be distinguished. The main peaks of each phase are highlighted with bold in table 4.

Table 4: Position of the Raman peaks in the characterized secondary phases, with the main modes highlighted in bold, and the best wavelength for specific phase detection.

Secondary phase	Raman shift [cm ⁻¹]	E _g (direct) [eV]	λ _{ex} [nm], [eV] *	Reference
β-Sb ₂ O ₃	75.4, 104.0, 140.2 , 186.2, 215.4, 224.5, 257.6, 283.1, 296.2 , 443.4, 488.6, 502.3, 597.2, 685.7	≈2.7	442, 2.72 (R)	This work Ref. 51
α-Sb ₂ O ₃	84, 124, 188 , 253 , 355, 372, 450 , 712	≈3.5	442, 2.72	Refs. 49, 51
Se (trigonal)	81.0, 112.7, 144.9, 236.4 , 240.7	≈1.9	633, 1.96 (R)	This work Ref. 52
Se (amorphous)	254.8	≈1.7-2.0	633, 1.96 (R)	This work Ref. 52
Sb	114.3 , 127.9, 151.3 , 255.9, 275.2	--	633, 1.96	This work Ref. 53

*(R) indicate conditions when resonant Raman scattering is expected

Finally, to show the possible influence of the used laser's power density to the Raman spectra of Sb₂Se₃ compound, the measurements at high power density of 785 nm laser were performed. In figure 8 it is seen that the evolution of the spectra for the low power densities from 21 to 42 W/cm² is reflected mainly in broadening of the peaks due to small local heating. With increasing of the power density up to 164 W/cm² the main mode became broad enough to reduce the resolution of the modes at 207 and 212 cm⁻¹, and the shift of the main peak to the lower wavenumbers becomes more relevant. Under the 180 W/cm² of laser power density the Sb₂Se₃ compound starts to decompose into α-Sb₂O₃, which is evident due to appearance of new peaks at 253, 372 and 450 cm⁻¹. Additionally, an increased asymmetry of the main peak at the low wavenumber side can be associated to appearance of the peak at 188 cm⁻¹ from α-Sb₂O₃ phase. As it was mentioned above, the former peak around 250 cm⁻¹ is the one usually observed by many researchers, and from the present study it adherence to a secondary phase is not discussible, either being α-Sb₂O₃ 253 cm⁻¹, Se-trigonal 236.4, 240.7 cm⁻¹ or Se-amorphous 254.8 cm⁻¹ peaks. Detection of α-Sb₂O₃ phase is compromised by overlapping of its most intense peaks at 188 and 253 cm⁻¹ with the main peaks of the Sb₂Se₃ and the Se amorphous phases, but appearance of the less intense peaks at 370 and 450 cm⁻¹ is a clear evidence of the formation of this phase. Note, that used laser power density at which the decomposition of Sb₂Se₃ starts is relatively low (~180 W/cm²), comparing to the common used laser power in micro Raman configuration with a spot diameter close to 1 μm (~ 30 kW/cm²), which implies the necessity to select very carefully the excitation laser power density.

Figure 8: Evolution of the room temperature Raman spectra and degradation of Sb_2Se_3 single crystal with the excitation power density of 785 nm laser. Appearance of peaks at 253, 372 and 450 cm^{-1} are associated to $\alpha\text{-Sb}_2\text{O}_3$ secondary phase formation. Inset: spectral range with emphasised peaks at 372 and 450 cm^{-1} for higher power densities explored.

Vibrational characterization of complete devices

Multi-wavelength Raman analysis was applied to the Sb_2Se_3 thin films and solar cells based on this absorber, synthesized in the way described in the Experimental section. Note, that the power conversion efficiency of the obtained device was 4.5 %, which is the typical range published for Sb_2Se_3 based devices (figure 9A). Previously the high potential of the Raman spectroscopy for the complete solar cell characterization was established.^{26,54,55} Indeed, clear methodologies for controlling the properties of different layers in thin film solar cells were shown.⁵¹ However, a fine reference Raman spectrum should be measured before developing any methodologies. The spectra measured on the bare absorber and on complete device under different excitation wavelengths are presented in figure 9B, together with the reference spectra measured on monocrystalline sample. In the spectra of complete device excited with 442 and 532 nm lasers the peak at 300 cm^{-1} is related to the CdS buffer layer. Here the use of the 442 nm excitation leads to a resonant condition with the CdS material and thus, a strong signal of its Raman peak do not allow to detect any peaks of the absorber layer, which implies to measure the Raman spectra of the absorber layer before completing the cell for the detection of possible Sb_2O_3 secondary phase. The spectra of the bare absorber measured under mentioned wavelengths were found to be different from the spectra of single crystal by a clear presence of a peak at 237 cm^{-1} , related to a trigonal selenium (t-Se) secondary phase. Widening of the main peak is observed in bare absorber layer, which is explained by expected worsening of the crystal quality in the thin film versus single crystal. Additionally, small variation of the relative

intensity of some of the Sb_2Se_3 peaks indicates difference in the preferential orientation of the thin film structure and the crystal plain of the monocrystalline sample, which, as it was mentioned above, can be potentially used for the control of thin film texture, i.e. the ribbons orientation.

Raman spectra measured under 633 nm excitation wavelength show an increase intensity of the trigonal selenium peak. This is mainly attributed to the resonant conditions for this secondary phase ($E_g(\text{Se}) \approx 1.9 \text{ eV}$, $E_{633\text{nm}} = 1.96 \text{ eV}$). This proves the preceded statement that measurement under 633 nm excitation is the most suitable for detection of low concentration of the elemental Se. In contrast, no clear evidences of peaks of elemental Sb were found in the measured spectra, which can be an indicator of the complete antimony incorporation in the Sb_2Se_3 structure. Taking into account observed presence of elemental selenium, the real chemical composition of the absorber could be closer to stoichiometric or even poor in selenium, which strongly influence the concentration of Se_{Sb} and V_{Sb} defects, which were found to be critical for the device performance.⁵⁶ Finally, in the spectra measured under 785 nm excitation wavelength the spectra of complete device, bare absorber and single crystal are highly similar and with a high signal to noise ratio. This allows to propose this excitation wavelength as the most suitable for the detection and analysis of Sb_2Se_3 compound, reducing the influence of the secondary phases contribution.

The combination of the different wavelengths provide a sensitive and non-destructive methodology for characterization of the absorber and/or full device based on Sb_2Se_3 thin film with a high sensitivity to detection of the most possible secondary phases.

Figure 9: A) J-V curve under illumination and in dark conditions of a representative device. B) Room temperature Raman spectra of the complete cell (dot line), bare absorber (dash-dot line) and single crystal (solid line) of Sb_2Se_3 measured under different excitation wavelengths. The peak of trigonal selenium phase at 236 cm^{-1} and of CdS buffer layer at 300 cm^{-1} are indicated as t-Se and CdS, respectively.

Conclusions

In this work, 15 of 30 Raman peak positions have been resolved at room temperature by multi-wavelength analysis and polarization study, and their symmetry was tentatively assigned. From the low temperature measurements, 13 peaks more were found in good agreement with theoretical predictions, and the positions at room temperature were confirmed. A good identification of the Raman peaks is crucial for the correct characterization of the material for all possible applications, and enables the possibility to potential evaluation of the concentration and type of atomic defects in the structure along with doping and other modifications of the structure. As a 1D material with a strong anisotropy of electrical conductivity, the assessment of the chain alignment is of a high importance, and the polarization Raman spectroscopy study opens the door to micro characterization of the material orientation with a fast and non-destructive technique.

The incongruences in the literature regarding the position and phase assignment of the material's Raman peaks has been treated in the secondary phase section. The importance of elemental selenium presence in the structure of the material and its effects on the electronic behaviour must be taken into account not to fall into the wrong interpretation of the experimental results. Additionally it is proposed a methodology based in multi-wavelength excitation for complete assessment of Sb_2Se_3 compound and their main secondary phases. Thus, we propose that characterization of the Sb_2Se_3 material could be properly performed under 785 nm excitation wavelength with minimal contribution of peaks from secondary phases. For the secondary phase detection and evaluation, the 442 nm excitation wavelength was found to be optimal for the antimony oxide species (only applicable in bare absorber), and the most suitable laser wavelength for elemental selenium detection was 633 nm (compatible with full devices characterization).

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